

where R=Et in pilocarpine, Ph·CHOH in pilosine and H in pilosinine ; pilocarpidine having R=C₂H₅ and NH for N·Me (*cf.* Jowett, *loc. cit.*).

Although the above structures for pilosine and pilosinine have been mainly based on some physiological and a few chemical properties, (*cf.* Pyman, *loc. cit.*) no attempts, as yet, have been made to settle the constitution of the alkaloids by synthesis. Syntheses of the formulated skeletons being necessary to come to a definite conclusion regarding their constitutions, the present investigation was undertaken to synthesise furan bodies from which the more complex system of the alkaloids could be built up.

The furan acid, 2-ketotetrahydrofuran-4-acetic acid, which is the parent compound of such lactonic acids and which is also present in pilosinine skeleton, has been described in the present paper. The methods adopted by the previous workers, Preobrashenski and others (*loc. cit.*), have been based on the syntheses of a higher homologous acid from a lower homologous one but the present synthesis has been achieved by the following simple manner, the method being of sufficiently general applicability.

These lactonic acids, 2-ketotetrahydro-furan-4-acetic acid and its derivatives, are isomeric with paraconic acids, and they are glutaric acids with two substituents, one in the α -position and the other in the β -position. The substituent in the α -position is an alkyl group (*cf.* Jowett, Pyman, *loc. cit.*), whereas the substituent in the β -position is always an oxymethyl group (-CH₂·OH), the hydroxyl group of which helps in the formation of the lactone ring. This necessitates the synthesis of these lactonic bodies from hydroxy-acetaldehyde and malonic ester following the well known synthesis of glutaric acid, the substituent in the α -position being subsequently introduced into the alkylidene dimalonic ester by the usual methods.

Methoxyacetaldehyde has been condensed with malonic ester in presence of piperidine yielding methoxyethylidene monomalonic ester (I) and methoxyethylidene dimalonic ester (II). The dimalonic ester, also obtainable from (I) by further treatment with malonic ester and piperidine, has been hydrolysed to β -methoxymethylglutaric acid (III) which ultimately on demethylation yields 2-ketotetrahydro-furan-4-acetic acid (IV) according to the following scheme.

of one of the reactive hydrogen atoms of the same ester by $C_6H_5 \cdot CH_2$ is in progress and this along with condensation of γ -methoxycrotonic ester (and also γ -ethoxy crotonic ester) with malonic and cyanoacetic esters will form the subject matter of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methoxyacetaldehyde.—Ethyleneglycol monomethyl ether (90 c.c.), dissolved in water (40 c.c.) was heated to boiling in a two necked 1000 c.c. round bottomed flask fitted with a dropping funnel and a fractionating column joined to a long condenser containing ice-water. A solution of pure sodium dichromate (132 g.) in water (160 c.c.) was mixed with concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 96 c.c.) and the mixture allowed to drop into the flask from the dropping funnel. The dropping of the liquid in the funnel was so regulated that the rate of addition was almost the same as the rate of distillation. The reaction was complete in about 45 minutes. The distillate coming at $99-101^\circ$ was collected in a flask placed in a freezing mixture bath. About 180 c.c. of methoxyacetyldehyde solution were obtained.

Ethyl Methoxyethylidene Monomalonate.—To the methoxyacetaldehyde solution (180 c.c.) ethyl malonate (100 c.c.) was added and after cooling the mixture in ice, piperidine (8-9 c.c.) was dropped into it. The mixture was kept in ice for 24 hours after which it was reheated on the water-bath for 7 hours. The liquid was then cooled, extracted with ether, washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, soda solution and water, dried over calcium chloride and finally distilled after removal of ether. The distillate was collected in three fractions: the first fraction containing mainly malonic ester, the second fraction (b.p. $120-140^\circ/8$ mm.) was repeatedly fractionated and collected at $128-130^\circ/8$ mm. [Found: C, 55.38; H, 7.50; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene) 217, 218. $C_{10}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 55.55; H, 7.40 per cent. M.W., 216]. That the liquid is unsaturated is proved by the fact that it decolourises bromine both in organic solvents and in water.

Ethyl Methoxyethylidene Dimalonate (1st method).—The third fraction obtained in the previous experiment was repeatedly fractionated and a slightly thick liquid was collected at $190-200^\circ/10$ mm. [Found: C, 54.12; H, 7.42. M.W. (cryoscopic), 373. $C_{17}H_{28}O_9$ requires C, 54.25; H, 7.44 per cent. M.W., 376].

Ethyl Methoxyethylidene Dimalonate (2nd method).—Ethyl methoxyethylidene monomalonate (20 g.) was mixed with excess of

malonic ester (30 g.) and piperidine (0.5 g.) and the mixture was heated on the water-bath for 6 hours. The liquid was then taken in ether and washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, soda solution and finally with water. The ether solution was then dried over calcium chloride and finally distilled at 190-200°/10 mm. [Found: C, 53.86; H, 7.65; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 375. $C_{17}H_{28}O_9$ requires C, 54.25; H, 7.44 per cent. M.W., 376].

In an experiment, glycol monomethyl ether (25 g.), malonic ester (105 g.) and a little piperidine (2.5 g.) were heated for 8 hours on the water-bath as in the above experiments. The materials, isolated in the usual way, were distilled and the liquids separated almost quantitatively into malonic ester and ethyleneglycol monomethylether without a trace of any higher boiling substance. This shows that ethyleneglycol monomethylether does not interfere with the condensation of the aldehyde with malonic ester.

β -Methoxymethylglutaric Acid.—A mixture of ethyl methoxyethylidene dimalonate (25 g.) and hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19, 50 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 6 hours during which the oil gradually disappeared. The liquid was in one experiment evaporated to dryness and distilled in vacuum and in another the acid solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether. The alkaline aqueous solution was then acidified and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. The distillate in both the experiments came over at 184-190°/4 mm. (Found: C, 47.5; H, 6.85; Equiv., 90. $C_7H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 47.7; H, 6.8 per cent. Equiv., 88).

β -Methoxymethylglutaric Anhydride.—The glutaric acid (5 g.) from the previous experiment was mixed with acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and heated under reflux on a sand-bath for 3 hours. The acetic anhydride was then removed on the water pump and the anhydride distilled at 145-152°/7 mm. It solidified at once and melted at 77-78°. (Found: C, 53.05; H, 6.5. $C_7H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 53.16; H, 6.3 per cent).

Ethyl β -Methoxymethylglutarate.—Methoxymethylglutaric acid (17.6 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (1.6 g. of Na in 200 c.c. of absolute alcohol) and refluxed for 9 hours with excess of ethyl bromide (55 g.). Alcohol and ethyl bromide were then distilled off as far as possible and the residual mass was then cooled, treated with water and extracted with ether in the usual way.

A liquid was collected at 125-135°/8 mm. [Found: C, 57·06; H, 8·58; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 228. $C_{11}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 56·90; H, 8·62 per cent. M.W., 232).

2-Ketotetrahydrofuran-4-acetic Acid.— β -Methoxymethylglutaric acid (3 g.) was heated at 160-180° for 3 hours in a sealed tube with hydrochloric acid (12 c.c., *d* 1·19). It was then cooled and the product filtered and distilled in vacuum after removal of water at the water pump. A viscous liquid, which solidified on cooling, was obtained at 200-208°/10 mm. It was repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ether when it melted at 87-88°. It is soluble in water, alcohol, chloroform, benzene, etc. It is not much soluble in ether, from which it can also be crystallised. (Found: C, 49·89; H, 5·31. $C_6H_8O_4$ requires C, 49·99; H, 5·55 per cent). Directly titrated in the cold with *N*/10-baryta and also with *N*/10 caustic soda it gave equiv. 144·4. $C_6H_8O_4$ requires (for one COOH- group) equiv., 144·0. When the acid was boiled with excess of NaOH for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and the excess of alkali titrated with *N*/10- H_2SO_4 , the equiv. wt. was 71·34. $C_6H_8O_4$ requires for one lactone group and one COOH group the equiv. wt. 72.

Ethyl methoxyethylidene dimalonate (5 g.) was heated to 180° for 5 hours in a sealed tube with concentrated HCl (*d* 1·19, 15 c.c.). The product when cold was neutralised with $NaHCO_3$ and extracted with ether. The solution of the sodium salt in water was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, gave on evaporation a thick oil which solidified on keeping. It was purified from ether-chloroform mixture, m.p. 87-88°; b.p. 200-208°/10 mm. (Found: C, 49·75; H, 5·64. $C_6H_8O_4$ requires C, 49·99, H, 5·5 per cent). Found: equiv., 143·3 with *N*/10-NaOH in the cold. Boiled with excess *N*/10-NaOH, equiv. was found to be 72·2. A mixed melting point of this with a sample obtained by the first method was determined and it was also 87-88°.

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